

Natural Colourants With Ancient Concept and Probable Uses

Tabassum Khair¹, Sujoy Bhusan², Koushik Choudhury², Ratna Choudhury³, Manabendra Debnath⁴ and Biplab De^{2*}

¹ Department of Pharmaceutical Sciences, Assam University, Silchar, Assam, India.

² Regional Institute of Pharmaceutical Science And Technology, Abhoynagar, Agartala, Tripura, India.

³ Rajnagar H. S. School, Agartala, Tripura, India.

⁴ Department of Human Physiology, Swami Vivekananda Mahavidyalaya, Mohanpur, Tripura, India.

*Corresponding author: Biplab De, E-mail: biplab_32@yahoo.co.in

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ABSTRACT:

The majority of natural colourants are of vegetable origin from plant sources –roots, berries, barks, leaves, wood and other organic sources such as fungi and lichens. In the medicinal and food products apart from active constituents there are several other ingredients present which are used for either ethical or technical reasons. Colouring agent is one of them, known as excipients. The discovery of man-made synthetic dye in the mid-19th century triggered a long decline in the large-scale market for natural dyes as practiced by the villagers and tribes. The continuous use of synthetic colours in textile and food industry has been found to be detrimental to human health, also leading to environmental degradation. Biocolours are extracted by the villagers and certain tribes from natural herbs, plants as leaves, fruits (rind or seeds), flowers (petals, stamens), bark or roots, minerals such as prussian blue, red ochre & ultramarine blue and are also of insect origin such as lac, cochineal and kermes. Biocolours have tremendous potential of application in food products. India has a great opportunity for export of natural dyes due to its vast plant wealth and rich traditional knowledge of using natural colorants as dye

Keyword: *Natural colourants, biocolours, natural dyes.*

INTRODUCTION

Natural colourants or dyes are those colourants that are derived from natural source such as plants, invertebrates or minerals. The majority of natural colourants are of vegetable origin from plant sources –roots, berries, barks, leaves, wood and other organic sources such as fungi and lichens. They are used as dyestuffs in textile industries, as colourants in foodstuffs, cosmetics and pharmaceutical products in order to mask unagreeable colour, pH indicators in various acid-base reactions. The use of such colouring matter is rooted in antiquity. Relics from the excavations of Harrapan culture have yielded evidence of ropes & fabric dyed with natural colours. The caves of Ajanta (The earliest dating back to the first century B.C.) still preserve the beauty of biocolours in their fullest splendour. In short, use of biocolours through the art of dyeing and printing is one of our richest heritages.

Archaeologists have found evidence of textile dyeing dating back to the Neolithic period. In China, dyeing with plants, barks and insects has been traced back more than 5,000 years. Throughout history, people have dyed their textiles using common, locally available materials, but scarce dyestuffs that produced brilliant and permanent colors such as the natural invertebrate dyes, Tyrian purple and crimson kermes, became highly priced luxury items in the ancient and medieval world. Plant-based dyes such as woad (*Isatis tinctoria*), indigo, saffron, and madder were raised commercially and were important trade goods in the economies of Asia and Europe.

In the medicinal and food products apart from active constituents there are several other ingredients present which are used for either ethical or technical reasons. These are called excipients. These include flavouring agents, colouring agents,

stabilizers, thickeners, antimicrobial preservatives, antioxidants etc. The colouring agents used for medicinal purpose are often identical to those used in food. Nowadays, there has been increasing demand for material of natural origin, particularly for colouring agents as because the toxic effects of several synthetic colourants has been observed. Also these natural colourants which are basically used for imparting colour may also overlap with their medicinal action. The essential subsidiary requirements for a medicinal and food colourants are non-toxicity and stability. Specific factors to be considered are effect of pH on colour, solubility in water and oil and stability to light, heat and sugar. [1 - 4].

Biocolours had to pay a very heavy price due to the development of the synthetic genre of dyestuff. Synthetic dyes gradually pushed natural dyes into oblivion due to their superiority in the speed of dyeing or printing and fastness of colours.

The discovery of man-made synthetic dye in the mid-19th century triggered a long decline in the large-scale market for natural dyes as practised by the villagers and tribals. Synthetic dyes, which could be produced in large quantities, quickly superseded natural dyes for the commercial textile production enabled by the industrial revolution and unlike natural dyes, were suitable for the synthetic fibers that followed. Fiber content determines the type of dye required for a fabric, and they are generally- Cellulose fibres: cotton, linen, hemp, ramie, bamboo, rayon; & Protein fibers: wool, angora, mohair, cashmere, silk, soy, leather.

But synthetic dyes are based on toxic raw materials and intermediaries. The effluents from the industry are one of the major causes of environment pollution. The continuous use of synthetic colours in textile and food industry has been found to be detrimental to human health, also leading to environmental

degradation.

Biocolours, on the other hand, are not only free from this handicap but could also assist the regeneration of the environment if plant varieties were cultivated on a commercial scale. Moreover, biocolours represent an apparently more sustainable source of colourants than their synthetic counterparts, which are derived from nonrenewable sources. [5]

Biocolours are extracted by the villagers and certain tribals from natural herbs, plants as leaves, fruits (rind or seeds), flowers (petals, stamens), bark or roots, minerals such as prussian blue, red ochre & ultramarine blue and are also of insect origin such as lac, cochineal and kermes. Every food is associated with a certain type of colour. The addition of colour gives food an attractive and appetizing appearance and enhances the acceptability. Hence, biocolours have tremendous potential of application in food products, for example as colouring material in soft drinks and other food products like sausages, jam, noodles, soft drinks etc. Among different colouring materials, red dye is used for more than a third of the modern world's food, either fresh or processed and also in pharmaceuticals. Similar demand also exists in the pharmaceutical industries because of the ban on red coloured dye amaranth. Here red biocolour could be a good substitute for the synthetic food colours. There has been an alarming outbreak of a number of diseases and disorders due to the over use of synthetic dyes in food production, drugs, medicines etc. This has led to synthetic colours in food products being looked down upon with certain amount of apprehension with regard to their safety and consequent shift to biocolours or herbal dyes in the world market.

The Indian Institute of Natural Resins and Gums (IINRG) at Ranchi has already transferred the technology of technical grade lac dye to several entrepreneurs. Recently the institute has developed a plant for pilot scale production of good food grade lac dye.

The total size of the world market for dyes, pigments and intermediates, estimated in 1999 as around US dollar 23 billion. Dyes and pigments constitute the largest segment with a market size of 1.3 million tones and a market value of 16 billion US dollar. Vegetable dyes constitute 03 billion US dollar and are expected to grow in the coming years. In 1998, Europe imported US dollar 53 million worth of "biocolours of animal or natural origin". The major importing countries were Germany (32%), France (17%), Italy (14%) and the U.K. (10%). According to report of the German Ministry of Food, Agriculture and Forestry, about 90000 tonnes of natural dyes can be produced every year. At present USA is one of the major importers of natural dyes.

In the early 21st century, the market for natural dyes in the fashion industry is experiencing a resurgence. Western consumers have become more concerned about the health and environmental impact of synthetic dyes in manufacturing and there is a growing demand for products that use natural dyes. The European Union, for example, has encouraged Indonesian batik cloth producers to switch to natural dyes to improve their export market in Europe. [6 - 9]

Dyes used in the fashion industry

The types of natural dyes currently in use by the global fashion industry include:

Animal source:

- Cochineal insect (red)
- Cow urine (Indian Yellow)
- Lac insect (red)
- Murex snail (purple)

- Octopus (sepia brown)

Plant source:

- Catechu or Cutch tree (brown)
- Gamboge tree resin (dark mustard yellow)
- Himalayan rubharb root (yellow)
- Indigofera plant (blue)
- Kamala tree (orange-yellow, golden yellow)
- Larkspur plant (yellow)
- Madder root (red, pink, orange)
- Myrrobalan fruit (yellow, green, black)
- Pomegranite peel (yellow)
- Weld herb (yellow)

Mineral source:

- Arsenic (green)
- Brown clay (umber brown)
- Cadmium (green, red, yellow, orange)
- Carbon (black)
- Chromium (yellow, green)
- Cinnabar (vermillion)
- Cobalt (blue)
- Copper (green, blue, purple)
- Hydrated iron oxide (ochre)
- Lead (white, yellow-red)
- Limonite clay (sienna)
- Titanium (white, beige, yellow, black)
- Zinc (white)

Common dyestuffs

Reds and pinks

A variety of plants produce red dyes, including a number of lichens henna, alkanet or dyer's bugloss (*Alkanna tinctoria*), asafoetida and madder. Madder (*Rubia tinctorum*) and related plants of the *Rubia* family are native to many temperate zones around the world, and have been used as a source of good red dye (rose madder) since prehistory. Turkey red was a strong, very fast red dye for cotton obtained from madder root. Turkey red was developed in India and spread to Turkey. Munjeet or Indian madder (*Rubia cordifolia*) is native to the Himalayas and other mountains of Asia and Japan. Munjeet was an important dye for the Asian cotton industry and is still used by craft dyers in Nepal.

Puccoon or bloodroot (*Sanguinaria canadensis*) is a popular red dye among Southeastern Native American basketweavers. Choctaw basketweavers additionally use sumac for red dye. A delicate rose color in Navajo rugs comes from avers also use rainwater and red dirt to create salmon-pink dyes.

Orange

Dyes that create reds and yellows can also yield oranges. Navajo dyers create orange dyes from one-seeded juniper, *Juniperus monosperma*, Navajo Tea, *Thelesperma gracile*, or alder bark.

Yellows

Yellow dyes are "about as numerous as red ones" and can be extracted from saffron, pomegranate rind, turmeric, onionskins, and a number of weedy flowering plants. Limited evidence suggests the use of weld (*Reseda luteola*), also called mignonette or dyer's rocket before the Iron Age, but it was an important dye of the ancient Mediterranean and Europe and is indigenous to England. Two brilliant yellow dyes of commercial importance in Europe from the 18th century are derived from trees of the Americas: quercitron from the inner bark of oaks native to North America and fustic from the dyer's mulberry tree (*Maclura tinctoria*) of the West Indies and Mexico.

In river cane basket weaving among Southeastern Woodlands

tribes in the Americas, butternut (*Juglans cinerea*) and yellow root (*Xanthorhiza simplicissima*) provide a rich yellow color. Chitimacha basket weavers have a complex formula for yellow that employs a dock plant (most likely *Rumex crispus*) for yellow. Navajo artists create yellow dyes from small snake-weed, brown onion skins, and rubber plant (*Parthenium incanum*). Rabbitbush (*Chrysothamnus*) and rose hips produce pale, yellow-cream colored dyes.

Fig. 1. Turmeric

Greens

If plants that yield yellow dyes are common, plants that yield green dyes are rare. Both woad and indigo have been used since ancient times in combination with yellow dyes to produce shades of green. Medieval and early modern England was especially known for its green dyes. The dyers of Lincoln, a great cloth town in the high Middle Ages, produced the Lincoln green cloth associated with Robin Hood by dyeing wool with woad and then over dyeing it yellow with weld or dyer's greenweed (*Genista tinctoria*), also known as dyer's broom. Woolen cloth mordanted with alum and dyed yellow with dyer's greenweed was overdyeed with woad and, later, indigo, to produce the once-famous Kendal green. This in turn fell out of fashion in the 18th century in favor of the brighter Saxon green, dyed with indigo and fustic.

Soft olive greens are also achieved when textiles dyed yellow are treated with an iron mordant. The dull green cloth common to the Iron Age Halstatt culture shows traces of iron, and was possibly colored by boiling yellow-dyed cloth in an iron pot. Indigenous peoples of the Northwest Plateau in North America used lichen to dye corn husk bags a beautiful sea green.

Navajo textile artist Nonabah Gorman Bryan developed a two-step process for creating green dye. First the Churro wool yarn is dyed yellow with sagebrush, *Artemisia tridentata*, and then it is soaked in black dye after bath. Red onion skins are also used by Navajo dyers to produce green.

Blues

China, and the West AfBlue colorants around the world were derived from indigo dye-bearing plants, primarily those in the genus *Indigofera* which are the natives of the tropics. The primary commercial indigo species in Asia was true indigo (*Indigofera tinctoria*). India is believed to be the oldest center of indigo dyeing in the Old World. It was a primary supplier of indigo dye to Europe as early as the Greco-Roman era. The association of India with indigo is reflected in the Greek word for the dye, which was *indikon*.

In temperate climate including Europe, indigo was obtained primarily from (*Isatis tinctoria*), an indigenous plant of Assyria and the Levant which has been grown in Northern Europe over 2,000 years, although from the 18th century it was mostly replaced by superior Indian indigo imported by the British East India Company. Woad was carried to New England in the 17th century and used extensively in America until native stands of indigo were discovered in Florida and the Carolinas. In Sumatra, indigo dye is

extracted from some species of *Marsdenia*. Other indigo-bearing dye plants include dyer's knotweed (*Polygonum tinctorum*) from Japan and the coasts of rican shrub *Lonchocarpus*

Purples

In medieval Europe, purple, violet, murrey and similar colors were produced by dyeing wool with woad or indigo in the fleece and then piece-dyeing the woven cloth with red dyes, either the common madder or the luxury dyes kermes and cochineal. Madder could also produce purples when used with alum. Brazilwood also gave purple shades with vitriol (H_2SO_4) or potash.

Choctaw artists traditionally used maple (*Acer* sp.) to create lavender and purple dyes. Purples can also be derived from lichens, and from the berries of White Bryony from the northern Rocky Mountain states and mulberry (*morus nigra*) (with an acid mordant).

Browns

Cutch is an ancient brown dye from the wood of acacia trees, particularly *Acacia catechu*, used in India for dyeing cotton. Cutch gives gray-browns with an iron mordant and olive-browns with copper.

Black walnut (*Juglans nigra*) is used by Cherokee artists to produce a deep brown approaching black. Today black walnut is primarily used to dye baskets but has been used in the past for fabrics and deerhide. Juniper, *Juniperus monosperma*, ashes provide brown and yellow dyes for Navajo people, as do the hulls of wild walnuts (*Juglans major*).

Grays and blacks

Choctaw dyers use maple (*Acer* sp.) for a grey dye. Naavajo weaver create black from mineral yellow ochre mixed with pitch from the pine tree (*Pinus edulis*) and the three-leaved sumac (*Rhus trilobata*). They also produce a cool grey dye with blue flower lupine and a warm grey from Juniper mistletoe (*Phoradendron juniperinum*).

Lichen

Dye-bearing lichens produce a wide range of greens, oranges, yellows, reds, browns, and bright pinks and purples. The lichen *Rocella tinctoria* was found along the Mediterranean Sea and was used by the ancient Phoenicians. In recent times, lichen dyes have been an important part of the dye traditions of Ireland, Scotland, and among native peoples of the southwest Intermontane Plateaus of the United State. Scottish lichen dyes include cudbear (also called archil in England and litmus in Holland), and crotle.

Fungi

Miriam C. Rice, (1918—2010) of Mendocino, California, pioneered research into using various mushrooms for natural dyes. She discovered mushroom dyes for a complete rainbow palette. Swedish and American mycologists, building upon Rice's research, have discovered sources for true blues (*Sarcodon squamosus*) and mossy greens (*Hydnellum geogenium*). *Hypholoma fasciculare* provides a yellow dye, and fungi such as *Phaeolus schweinitzii* and *Pisolithus tinctorius* are used in dyeing textiles and paper.

NATURAL COLOURANTS USED IN PHARMACEUTICAL PRODUCTS

RED POPPY PETALS

Red poppy petals consist of dried whole or fragmented petals of *Papaver rhoeas* of family Papaveraceae. It is widely grown in North Africa, North America, Australia, New Zealand and temperate Asia. When harvested the petals are dark violet in colour and the upper surface is shiny and smooth in appearance. But the dried commercial product is digny violet and get clumped. Its taste is mucilaginous and slightly bitter. The colour of red poppy petals

is due to anthocyanidins including gentiobioside of cyanidin. The drug on treatment with acid becomes scarlet while alkali turns it greenish-blue. Alkaloids with little toxicity and mucilage are also present. They were traditionally used as expectorant but now they are used as colouring agent in infusions and syrups.

SAFFRON

Saffron consists of the dried stigmas and top of the the styles of *Crocus sativus* of family Iridaceae. The major producers of saffron are China, Spain, Iran and in India it is grown in Kashmir. The corms are planted in July or August in soil carefully prepared during the last autumn. Saffron, often called hay-saffron, occurs in loose masses consisting of reddish brown stigmas along which the yellow pieces of top to styles can also be seen. It has sweet aromatic odour and a bitter taste. When chewed the saliva is coloured orange-yellow

Saffron consists a number of carotenoid pigments. Safranal, a hydrolysis product of picrocin is responsible for characteristic odour and taste of saffron. It is widely used as colouring and flavouring agent. Recent work has demonstrated anticancer, antiarthritic, antihypertensive activities of saffron due to the antioxidant properties of its constituents.

MARIGOLD FLOWERS

Marigold, commonly known as African marigold is obtained by the extraction of xanthophyll pigments from the florets of *Tagetes erecta* of family Compositae. It is commercially grown in Mexico, Peru and Ecuador. Each plant is estimated to produce about 330 mg of xanthophylls. Except flavoxanthin, the xanthophyll has same carbon skeleton as that of carotene.

RED BEETROOT

The powdered red beetroot obtained from *Beta vulgaris* of family Chenopodiaceae, gives red pigment betanin is widely used as non-toxic food and pharmaceutical colourants. Betanin is a nitrogen-containing glycoside which on hydrolysis gives the aglycone betanidin and glucose. Apart from its use as as food and colourant, it has various medicinal activities including that of free-radical scavenger and also hepatoprotective activity.

MONASCUS

Monascus purpureus is a mould which, when grown on cooked or autoclaved rice and then whole dried and pulverized, gives a food colourant. The strains of mould producing dark red monascorubin is of particular importance. It is often used as edible, non-toxic substituent of expensive cochineal.

RED ROSE PETALS

The petals of the Provence rose, *Rosa gallica* are used for acid infusions of rose. Due to its astringent property and colouring principles, the infusions are used as vehicles for gargles containing alum or tannin. The petal extracts cannot be prescribed with alkaline salts because of its anthocyanine constituents.

ANNATTO

Annatto seeds are obtained from *Bixa orellana* of family Bixaceae. They are characterized by having edible carotenoid pigment on their surface. The plant is a shrub or small tree, cultivated mainly in northern South America, West Indies, Tropical Asia and Africa for its seed or as an instrumental. Ecuador, India, Kenya and Peru are the primary producers. Two varieties of white and pink flower are available. In food industry it is considered as the safer food additive. The stability of the dye in fixed oil makes it suitable for use in dairy industry.

Bixin, a C₂₄-apocarotenoid is the main constituent of the dye. Removal of methyl ester group of bixin gives the dicarboxylic acid norbixin which forms the basis of water soluble annatto dye. Apart from its use in food industry, annatto and bixin are used in

coloured coating of tablets, pills, granules and herbal medicine preparations.

COCHINEAL

Cochineal is an important colourant and indicator and consist of the dried, female insect, *Dactylopius coccus*, containing egg and larvae. It is indigenous to Central America. The other producers are China, Bolivia, Mexico. It contains about 10% of carminic acid, a brilliant purple, water-soluble colouring matter, which is a c-glycoside anthraquinone. The insect also contain 10% of fat and 2% of wax.

HEENA

Henna consists of dried leaves of *Lawsonia inermis* of family Lythraceae, a shrub which is cultivated in Egypt, India and Ceylon. The leaves are greenish-brown to brown in colour. Henna contains colouring matter lawsone, a hydroxynepthoquinone, various phenolic glycosides, coumarins, xanthenes, quinoids, glucosides, flavonoids, fats, resin and henna-tannin. Henna is commonly use as a dye for hair but the astringent stem-bark of *L. inermis* is traditionally used for the treatment of jaundice, enlargement of liver and spleen and for various skin diseases.

Few Traditional uses of natural colour and relevant aspects:

Haldi i.e. Turmeric consist of dried as well as fresh rhizomes of the plant- *Curcuma longa / domestica*, F: Zingiberaceae. Generally it is used to colour curry. Traditionally (e.g. Tribal people of Tripura) it is used to colour thread. The turmeric is washed first with water and thrashed in a pot. Then CaHCO₃ is mixed gently with the yellow colored extract solution, which gives it red colour. These red and yellow colours both are utilized for coloring the threads. Fruit of *Mallotus philippinensis* (F: Euphorbiaceae) i.e. *Kamala* provides reddish color in silk and wool. Oil is used a hair-fixer and added in ointment. Wood pulp is suitable for writing and printing paper. The fresh green leaves of *Segun/Saigun* (*Tectona grandis*, F: Verbenaceae) in boiled hot water gives red colored liquid and is used to color thread. Unripe Betel nut/Areca nut (*Areca catechu*, F: Palmae) on boiling in water gives reddish brown color, which is used in thread coloring and afterwards is generally dried in sunlight. [1,6,9-15]

Fig. 2. Saigun

Fig.3. Areca nut

CONCLUSION:

India has a great opportunity for export of natural dyes due to its vast plant wealth and rich traditional knowledge of using natural colorants as dye. However, although bio-colors used in food are screened for safety, toxicological information for most of these natural colors used as coloring material in soft drinks & other food products is sparse. There is a tendency to assume that natural products are safer & better than synthetic products because they are natural and bio-adjusted, however, the safety of bio-colors need to be proved if they are to be used more widely in food products and commercial processes.

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